

Supplementary Material

For the manuscript:

Reduced Testicular Function in Young Men possibly associated with Maternal Exposure to Phthalates during Pregnancy

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Supplementary Table 1 Phthalate diesters, their metabolites and LODs

Phthalate diester	Abbreviation	Human metabolite	Abbreviation	Alternative abbreviation	LOD (ng/mL)
Di-methyl phthalate	DMP	Mono-methyl phthalate	MMP		0.27
Di-ethyl phthalate	DEP	Mono-ethyl phthalate	MEP		0.43
Di-iso-propyl phthalate	DiPrP	Mono-iso-propyl phthalate	MiPrP		0.07
Di-n-propyl phthalate	DnPrP	Mono-n-propyl phthalate	MnPrP	MPrP	0.11
Di-iso-butyl phthalate	DiBP	Mono-iso-butyl phthalate	MiBP		0.16
		Mono-(2-hydroxy-iso-butyl) phthalate	2OH-MiBP	MHBP	0.25
Di-n-butyl phthalate	DnBP	Mono-n-butyl phthalate	MnBP		0.17
		Mono-(3-hydroxybutyl) phthalate	3OH-MnBP	MHBP	0.25
Butylbenzyl phthalate	BBzP	Mono-benzyl phthalate	MBzP		0.03
Di-n-pentyl phthalate	DnPeP	Mono-n-pentyl phthalate	MnPeP		0.10
Di-(2-ethyl-hexyl) phthalate	DEHP	Mono-(2-ethyl-hexyl) phthalate	MEHP		0.07
		Mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate	5OH-MEHP	MEHHP	0.05
		Mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate	5oxo-MEHP	MEOHP	0.06
		Mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate	5cx-MEPP	MECPP	0.07
		Mono-(2-carboxymethyl-hexyl) phthalate	2cx-MMHP	MCMHP	0.12
Di-n-hexyl phthalate	DnHxP	Mono-n-hexyl phthalate	MnHxP		0.04
		Mono-(5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate	5OH-MHxP	MHHxP	0.02
		Mono-(5-carboxypentyl) phthalate	5cx-MPeP	MCPeP	0.02
Di-cyclohexyl phthalate	DCHP	Mono-cyclohexyl phthalate	MCHP		0.23
Di-n-heptyl phthalate	DnHpP	Mono-n-heptyl phthalate	MnHpP	MHpP	0.03
		Mono-(6-hydroxyheptyl) phthalate	6OH-MHpP	MHHpP	0.01
		Mono-(6-carboxyhexyl) phthalate	6cx-MHxP	MCHxP	0.03
Di-octyl phthalate	DnOP	Mono-n-octyl phthalate	MnOP	MOP	0.03
		Mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate	MCPP ^a		0.03
Di-iso-nonyl phthalate	DiNP	Mono-iso-nonyl phthalate	MiNP		0.14
		Mono-hydroxy-iso-nonyl phthalate	OH-MiNP	MHiNP	0.03
		Mono-oxo-iso-nonyl phthalate	oxo-MiNP	MOiNP	0.02
		Mono-carboxy-iso-octyl phthalate	cx-MiOP	MciOP	0.04
Di-iso-decylphthalate	DiDP	Mono-iso-decyl phthalate	MiDP		0.16
		Mono-(hydroxy-iso-decyl) phthalate	OH-MiDP	MHiDP	0.02
		Mono-(oxo-iso-decyl) phthalate	oxo-MiDP	MOiDP	0.02
		Mono-(carboxy-iso-nonyl) phthalate	cx-MiNP	MciNP	0.02

^aMCPP is the major metabolite of DnOP but is not specific for DnOP.

LOD, limit of detection.

Supplementary Table 2 Unadjusted reproductive outcomes in the 100 young men

	n	Median (IQR)
Reproductive hormones		
FSH (U/L)	100	2.95 (2.13, 4.39)
Inhibin B (pg/mL)	100	190 (144, 238)
LH (U/L)	100	4.02 (2.99, 5.11)
INSL3 (µg/L)	100	1.26 (1.05, 1.69)
Testosterone (nmol/L)	100	20.2 (17.5, 24.4)
SHBG (nmol/L)	100	34 (28, 40)
Oestradiol (nmol/L)	100	93 (81, 110)
Free testosterone (pmol/L)	100	441 (376, 499)
Free testosterone/LH	100	108 (85, 144)
Testosterone/LH	100	5.42 (3.84, 6.76)
Inhibin B/FSH	100	69 (33, 107)
IGF-1 (µg/L)	100	280 (250, 326)
IGFBP-3 (µg/L)	100	4394 (4069, 4868)
Clinical parameters		
Penile length (cm)	89	9.20 (8.50, 9.60)
Penile width (cm)	89	3.30 (3.00, 3.50)
Mean testis volume, ultrasound (mL)	90	13.98 (12.15, 15.87)
APD (cm)	87	12.70 (12.00, 13.50)
ASD (cm)	87	5.90 (5.10, 7.10)
Semen parameters		
Semen volume (mL)	98	3.1 (2.0, 4.1)
Sperm concentration (million/mL)	98	52 (23, 81)
Total sperm count (million)	98	134 (63, 280)
Progressively motile (%)	98	60 (47, 70)
Normal morphology (%)	98	7.5 (5.0, 10.5)

IQR, interquartile range; FSH, follicle-stimulating hormone; INSL3, insulin-like factor 3; SHBG, sex hormone binding globulin; LH, luteinizing hormone; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor; IGFBP-3, insulin-like growth factor-binding protein 3; APD, anopenile distance; ASD, anoscrotal distance.

Supplementary Table 3 Concentrations of phthalate metabolites (ng/mL) (measured in >50% of samples) in included vs. excluded maternal serum samples taken during pregnancy

	Participants (n=100)		Non-participants (n=264)		p
	% ≥ LOD	Median (IQR)	% ≥ LOD	Median (IQR)	
MEP	98.0	2.30 (0.72, 7.44)	99.2	3.01 (1.08, 6.91)	0.3
MiBP	100	3.18 (1.80, 6.87)	100	3.42 (1.58, 6.38)	0.6
2OH-MiBP	94.0	0.63 (0.40, 0.90)	95.8	0.71 (0.51, 0.99)	0.035
MnBP	99.0	31.2 (4.44, 55.0)	97.7	28.7 (4.00, 55.6)	0.8
MEHP	100	5.09 (2.63, 7.30)	100	5.40 (2.91, 7.76)	0.4
5cx-MEPP	100	0.46 (0.31, 0.69)	100	0.44 (0.32, 0.68)	0.8
2cx-MMHP	93.0	0.37 (0.210, 0.62)	94.7	0.35 (0.24, 0.54)	>0.9
MiNP	95.0	1.26 (0.78, 1.97)	97.0	1.21 (0.60, 2.03)	0.6
cx-MiOP	53.0	0.09 (<LOD, 0.17)	52.3	0.08 (<LOD, 0.15)	0.7
MiDP	91.0	3.53 (1.69, 5.45)	93.2	3.59 (1.41, 6.26)	0.8
cx-MiNP	74.0	0.18 (<LOD, 0.50)	68.9	0.16 (<LOD, 0.32)	0.15
Σprimary	100	49.1 (19.3, 79.5)	100	51.7 (23.6, 75.5)	0.7
Σsecondary	100	1.66 (1.17, 2.28)	100	1.67 (1.30, 2.10)	>0.9

LOD, limit of detection; IQR, interquartile range. Phthalate metabolite abbreviations are presented in Supplementary Table 1.

Σprimary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σsecondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP.

Significant p values are highlighted in bold.

Supplementary Table 4 Maternal serum concentration of phthalate metabolites and reproductive hormone concentrations (LH/Leydig cell axis) in adult sons

	LH		INSL3		Testosterone		SHBG		Free testosterone		Testosterone/LH		Free testosterone/LH	
	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a
MEP	1.0 (-2.4-4.4)	1.2 (-2.5-5.1)	0.0 (0.0-0.0)	0.0 (0.0-0.1)	-1.0 (-3.2-1.2)	0.2 (-2.1-2.5)	-0.4 (-3.4-2.7)	1.0 (-2.0-4.2)	-0.6 (-2.6-1.4)	0.0 (-2.1-2.2)	-2.0 (-5.5-1.7)	-1.0 (-4.9-3.0)	-1.6 (-4.9-1.8)	-1.2 (-4.9-2.7)
MiBP	5.2 (-0.7-11.4)	4.8 (-2.2-12.4)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	3.0 (-0.8-7)	0.7 (-3.4-5.1)	3.0 (-2.3-8.5)	1.1 (-4.6-7.0)	1.4 (-2.0-5.0)	-0.1 (-4.0-4.0)	-2 (-8.1-4.4)	-3.9 (-10.7-3.4)	-3.5 (-9.0-2.3)	-4.7 (-11.2-2.3)
2OH-MiBP	-1.7 (-9.8-7)	-0.5 (-9.1-8.9)	0.0 (-0.2-0.1)	0.0 (-0.2-0.1)	4.7 (-0.9-10.6)	3.3 (-2.1-9.0)	4.3 (-3.4-12.6)	0.8 (-6.4-8.6)	3.4 (-1.7-8.7)	4.0 (-1.2-9.4)	6.6 (-2.8-16.9)	3.8 (-5.6-14.2)	5.2 (-3.4-14.6)	4.5 (-4.6-14.5)
MnBP	4.5 (1.2-7.8)	5.5 (1.2-9.9)	0.0 (0.0-0.1)	0.0 (0.0-0.1)	1.7 (-0.4-3.9)	0.4 (-2.2-3.0)	0.9 (-2.0-3.9)	0.3 (-3.1-3.9)	1.6 (-0.4-3.5)	0.5 (-1.9-3.0)	-2.6 (-6-0.9)	-4.8 (-8.9-(-0.5))	-2.8 (-5.9-0.4)	-4.7 (-8.6-(-0.5))
MEHP	8.9 (1.2-17.2)	12.9 (4.1-22.5)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	5.1 (0.1-10.2)	5.8 (0.7-11.3)	1.8 (-4.9-9.0)	0.7 (-6.1-8.1)	4.7 (0.3-9.4)	6.3 (1.4-11.5)	-3.6 (-11.2-4.7)	-6.3 (-14.3-2.5)	-3.9 (-10.9-3.7)	-5.8 (-13.6-2.7)
5cx-MEPP	0.4 (-7.2-8.6)	0.1 (-7.8-8.7)	0.1 (0.0-0.2)	0.0 (-0.1-0.2)	2.3 (-2.8-7.6)	1.8 (-3.1-6.9)	4.6 (-2.5-12.3)	6.1 (-0.7-13.4)	-0.5 (-5.0-4.2)	-2.0 (-6.5-2.7)	1.9 (-6.5-11)	1.7 (-6.8-10.9)	-0.9 (-8.4-7.3)	-2.1 (-10.0-6.5)
2cx-MMHP	2.8 (-3.8-9.8)	2.2 (-4.9-9.8)	0.1 (0.0-0.2)	0.1 (0.0-0.2)	2.3 (-2.0-6.8)	2.9 (-1.4-7.4)	2.7 (-3.3-9.0)	4.4 (-1.5-10.7)	0.9 (-3.0-5.0)	0.4 (-3.6-4.6)	-0.4 (-7.4-7.1)	0.7 (-6.7-8.6)	-1.8 (-8.2-5.0)	-1.7 (-8.7-5.7)
MiNP	7.1 (0.8-13.8)	8.3 (1.5-15.6)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	-1.4 (-5.3-2.7)	-0.1 (-4.1-4.0)	-1.4 (-6.8-4.3)	-0.2 (-5.6-5.4)	-0.8 (-4.4-2.9)	-0.3 (-4.0-3.7)	-7.9 (-13.8-(-1.7))	-7.8 (-13.9-(-1.2))	-7.4 (-12.8-(-1.6))	-7.9 (-13.8-(-1.6))
cx-MiOP	-1.7 (-8.0-5.0)	-1.7 (-8.3-5.4)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	3.1 (-1.2-7.6)	3.3 (-0.9-7.7)	3.0 (-3.0-9.3)	4.4 (-1.3-10.5)	1.6 (-2.3-5.7)	0.9 (-3.0-5.0)	4.9 (-2.4-12.7)	5.2 (-2.3-13.1)	3.4 (-3.3-10.5)	2.7 (-4.4-10.3)
MiDP	2.6 (-2.5-7.9)	4.2 (-1.2-9.8)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	-0.2 (-3.4-3.2)	0.0 (-3.2-3.3)	-0.8 (-5.3-3.8)	-2.0 (-6.2-2.4)	-0.1 (-3.1-2.9)	0.6 (-2.4-3.8)	-2.7 (-7.9-2.9)	-4.0 (-9.2-1.5)	-2.6 (-7.5-2.5)	-3.4 (-8.5-2.0)
cx-MiNP	2.0 (-1.4-5.5)	1.6 (-2-5.3)	0.0 (0.0-0.0)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	1.3 (-0.9-3.6)	0.7 (-1.5-2.9)	-0.2 (-3.3-2.9)	-0.3 (-3.2-2.7)	1.6 (-0.4-3.6)	0.9 (-1.2-3)	-0.7 (-4.3-3.1)	-0.9 (-4.6-3.0)	-0.4 (-3.8-3.1)	-0.7 (-4.3-3.1)
Σ primary	11.1 (4.7-18)	13.0 (5.4-21.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	1.8 (-2.3-6.1)	0.4 (-4.0-5.0)	0.8 (-4.9-6.7)	-0.6 (-6.5-5.7)	1.7 (-2.1-5.6)	1.0 (-3.2-5.4)	-8.4 (-14.3-(-2))	-11.1 (-17.5-(-4.3))	-8.5 (-14-(-2.7))	-10.6 (-16.8-(-3.9))
Σ secondary	3.4 (-5.3-12.9)	3.7 (-5.3-13.5)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	0.0 (-0.1-0.1)	4.2 (-1.5-10.4)	3.3 (-2.2-9.1)	2.6 (-5.3-11.1)	2.5 (-4.9-10.5)	3.3 (-2.0-8.8)	2.2 (-3.0-7.7)	0.8 (-8.5-11)	-0.3 (-9.5-9.7)	-0.1 (-8.7-9.2)	-1.4 (-10.2-8.2)

^aModels were adjusted for maternal smoking during pregnancy [Y/N], maternal age at delivery, gestational week at maternal serum sampling, smoking habits [non-smoker, occasionally, daily], total body fat percentage of the young man and time of day for serum sampling.

LH, luteinizing hormone; INSL3, insulin-like factor 3; SHBG, sex hormone binding globulin; CI, confidence interval.

Phthalate metabolite abbreviations are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Σ primary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σ secondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP.

Effect estimates (β) have the unit percentage and should be interpreted as the median change in the outcome when the serum concentration of the phthalate metabolite doubles. For example, LH increases with 4.5% (1.2-17.2) when MnBP doubles in concentration in the adjusted model. Please note that as INSL3 concentrations were included in models untransformed, the shown effect estimates are to be interpreted as the absolute change when exposure doubles. Significant associations are highlighted in bold.

Supplementary Table 5 Maternal serum concentration of phthalate metabolites and reproductive hormone concentrations (FSH/Sertoli cell axis, oestradiol and growth factors) in adult sons

	FSH		Inhibin B		Inhibin B/FSH		Estradiol		IGF-1		IGFBP-3	
	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a
MEP	-1.1 (-5.9–3.9)	-1.9 (-7.2–3.6)	1.6 (-1.5–4.9)	2.5 (-0.9–6.2)	2.8 (-4.4–10.5)	4.6 (-3.6–13.4)	1.7 (-0.6–4.1)	2.1 (-0.4–4.6)	-0.2 (-2.1–1.7)	-0.7 (-2.6–1.3)	0.7 (-0.6–2.1)	0.1 (-1.3–1.4)
MiBP	4.1 (-4.3–13.3)	2.9 (-7.2–14)	1.3 (-4.1–7.0)	1.9 (-4.5–8.7)	-2.8 (-14.2–10.2)	-1.0 (-14.9–15.2)	1.8 (-2.1–6.0)	0.0 (-4.5–4.8)	1.8 (-1.5–5.2)	1.0 (-2.6–4.8)	1.5 (-0.8–3.8)	1.6 (-0.9–4.1)
2OH-MiBP	-7.4 (-18.1–4.6)	-8.9 (-20.1–3.8)	6.9 (-1.1–15.7)	6.0 (-2.4–15.1)	15.5 (-3.5–38.3)	16.3 (-4.0–41)	-0.1 (-5.7–5.9)	0.7 (-5.1–6.9)	-3.5 (-8.0–1.2)	-4.8 (-9.1–(-0.3))	-2.2 (-5.3–1.1)	-2.6 (-5.6–0.5)
MnBP	-0.2 (-4.9–4.6)	-2.1 (-8.0–4.3)	0.4 (-2.6–3.5)	1.7 (-2.3–5.8)	0.7 (-6.1–7.9)	3.8 (-5.3–13.8)	1.2 (-1.0–3.5)	-0.3 (-3.1–2.6)	-0.4 (-2.2–1.4)	-0.7 (-3.0–1.5)	-0.4 (-1.6–0.9)	-0.5 (-2.0–1.0)
MEHP	2.2 (-8.4–13.9)	-2.0 (-13.6–11.2)	2.9 (-4.0–10.4)	4.3 (-3.6–12.9)	0.8 (-14.2–18.3)	6.5 (-11.5–28.0)	7.6 (2.4–13.0)	8.5 (2.8–14.5)	0.1 (-4.1–4.4)	-0.6 (-5.0–4.0)	1.7 (-1.2–4.7)	1.3 (-1.7–4.4)
5cx-MEPP	-3.0 (-13.4–8.7)	-3.1 (-14.1–9.4)	1.6 (-5.6–9.3)	2.7 (-4.8–10.8)	4.7 (-11.5–23.7)	6.0 (-11.2–26.5)	-0.6 (-5.7–4.9)	-0.3 (-5.6–5.3)	-4.0 (-8.1–0.2)	-2.4 (-6.6–1.9)	0.5 (-2.5–3.6)	1.3 (-1.6–4.2)
2cx-MMHP	2.1 (-7.3–12.5)	0.9 (-9.2–12.2)	-1.5 (-7.4–4.9)	0.2 (-6.3–7.1)	-3.5 (-16.3–11.3)	-0.7 (-15.0–15.9)	0.5 (-3.9–5.2)	0.4 (-4.3–5.3)	-3.5 (-7.0–0.1)	-2.9 (-6.5–0.8)	0.4 (-2.2–3.0)	0.0 (-2.5–2.6)
MiNP	5.3 (-3.7–15.2)	4.4 (-5.4–15.2)	-0.2 (-5.8–5.8)	1.2 (-4.9–7.7)	-5.2 (-17.0–8.2)	-3.0 (-16.1–12.1)	0.2 (-3.9–4.6)	1.4 (-3.0–6.0)	2.7 (-0.8–6.3)	3.4 (-0.2–7.0)	3.3 (0.9–5.7)	3.1 (0.7–5.4)
cx-MiOP	3.8 (-5.7–14.2)	2.6 (-7.4–13.7)	-3.7 (-9.5–2.4)	-2.3 (-8.4–4.3)	-7.2 (-19.4–6.8)	-4.8 (-18.1–10.7)	0.9 (-3.6–5.6)	1.8 (-2.8–6.6)	-2.6 (-6.2–1.1)	-1.7 (-5.2–2.0)	-0.7 (-3.2–1.9)	0.2 (-2.2–2.7)
MiDP	-0.1 (-7.2–7.5)	-1.4 (-8.9–6.6)	-0.7 (-5.3–4.1)	-1.3 (-6.1–3.7)	-0.6 (-10.8–10.8)	0.1 (-10.8–12.4)	-1.7 (-5.0–1.8)	-0.4 (-3.9–3.2)	1.1 (-1.7–4.0)	0.8 (-2.0–3.7)	0.9 (-1.1–2.9)	0.8 (-1.1–2.7)
cx-MiNP	1.9 (-3.0–7.0)	1.5 (-3.7–7.1)	-1.0 (-4.1–2.2)	-0.6 (-3.9–2.8)	-2.8 (-9.6–4.5)	-2.1 (-9.4–5.9)	-0.2 (-2.5–2.1)	-0.6 (-3.0–1.8)	-1.3 (-3.1–0.6)	-1.2 (-3.0–0.7)	-0.9 (-2.2–0.4)	-0.7 (-2.0–0.5)
Σprimary	0.9 (-8.0–10.6)	-2.8 (-12.9–8.3)	2.1 (-3.8–8.4)	4.3 (-2.6–11.6)	1.2 (-11.6–15.9)	7.3 (-8.5–25.9)	3.5 (-0.8–8.0)	1.6 (-3.3–6.7)	2.0 (-1.6–5.7)	1.0 (-2.9–5)	1.5 (-0.9–4.1)	0.8 (-1.8–3.4)
Σsecondary	-1.8 (-13.6–11.6)	-1.9 (-14.2–12.2)	2.1 (-6.0–10.8)	2.7 (-5.6–11.8)	3.9 (-13.9–25.5)	4.7 (-14.0–27.5)	-1.0 (-6.8–5.2)	-0.5 (-6.3–5.7)	-5.6 (-10.1–(-0.9))	-4.6 (-9.0–0.1)	-2.3 (-5.5–1.1)	-1.6 (-4.7–1.6)

^aModels were adjusted for maternal smoking during pregnancy [Y/N], maternal age at delivery, gestational week at maternal serum sampling, smoking habits [non-smoker, occasionally, daily], total body fat percentage of the young man and time of day for serum sampling.

FSH, follicle-stimulating hormone; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor; IGFBP-3, insulin-like growth factor-binding protein 3; CI, confidence interval. Phthalate metabolite abbreviations are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Σ primary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σ secondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP.

Effect estimates (β) have the unit percentage and should be interpreted as the median change in the outcome when the serum concentration of the phthalate metabolite doubles. Significant associations are highlighted in bold.

Supplementary Table 6 Maternal serum concentration of phthalate metabolites and penile dimensions, testis volume and anogenital distance in adult sons

	Penile length		Penile width		Testis volume		APD		ASD	
	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a
MEP	0.0 (-1.2–1.1)	0.0 (-1.3–1.2)	-0.7 (-1.8–0.5)	-0.7 (-2.1–0.6)	1.2 (-1.0–3.5)	1.6 (-0.9–4.0)	-0.6 (-1.4–0.2)	-0.6 (-1.4–0.3)	-0.6 (-2.9–1.9)	-0.7 (-3.3–1.9)
MiBP	-3.3 (-5–(-1.5))	-3.1 (-5.1–(-1.1))	0.1 (-1.9–2.1)	-0.3 (-2.6–2.0)	0.4 (-3.3–4.2)	2.6 (-1.5–7.0)	1.1 (-0.3–2.5)	1.3 (-0.1–2.8)	2.6 (-1.4–6.8)	0.9 (-3.6–5.6)
2OH-MiBP	1.4 (-1.4–4.3)	1.1 (-1.8–4.1)	-0.5 (-3.4–2.4)	-0.6 (-3.7–2.5)	3.9 (-1.6–9.7)	4.9 (-0.8–11.0)	-1.0 (-3.0–1.0)	-0.3 (-2.2–1.7)	-3.2 (-8.7–2.7)	-3.9 (-9.6–2.1)
MnBP	-1.4 (-2.5–(-0.3))	-1.3 (-2.6–0.0)	-0.6 (-1.8–0.5)	-1.2 (-2.6–0.2)	-0.6 (-2.8–1.6)	0.8 (-1.8–3.5)	0.0 (-0.8–0.8)	-0.2 (-1.2–0.7)	0.7 (-1.7–3.2)	-0.3 (-3.2–2.7)
MEHP	-2.4 (-4.8–0.1)	-1.8 (-4.4–0.9)	-0.8 (-3.3–1.8)	-1.1 (-3.9–1.8)	4.3 (-0.5–9.4)	5.7 (0.6–11.1)	1.2 (-0.6–3.1)	1.4 (-0.5–3.3)	1.2 (-4.1–6.7)	-0.1 (-5.8–5.9)
5cx-MEPP	-1.1 (-3.6–1.4)	-2.0 (-4.5–0.6)	-1.1 (-3.6–1.5)	-1.5 (-4.2–1.2)	-0.1 (-4.9–4.9)	-0.3 (-5.2–4.9)	-0.6 (-2.5–1.3)	-0.4 (-2.3–1.5)	-3.0 (-8.3–2.6)	-2.5 (-8.1–3.3)
2cx-MMHP	-0.8 (-3.0–1.4)	-1.8 (-4–0.5)	-0.8 (-3.0–1.4)	-1.2 (-3.6–1.3)	-0.7 (-4.8–3.6)	-0.2 (-4.5–4.3)	-0.4 (-2.0–1.2)	-0.8 (-2.4–0.8)	-0.3 (-4.9–4.5)	0.4 (-4.5–5.5)
MiNP	-0.3 (-2.2–1.7)	-0.6 (-2.6–1.5)	-1.5 (-3.5–0.4)	-2.2 (-4.3–(-0.1))	-0.8 (-4.5–3.1)	-1.0 (-4.9–3.1)	0.4 (-1–1.8)	0.3 (-1.1–1.8)	-0.2 (-4.3–4.0)	-0.7 (-5.1–3.9)
cx-MiOP	-0.2 (-2.3–2.0)	-0.7 (-2.8–1.5)	-1.4 (-3.5–0.7)	-1.8 (-4.0–0.4)	-0.3 (-4.3–4.0)	0.3 (-3.8–4.6)	-0.8 (-2.3–0.8)	-1.3 (-2.7–0.2)	-1.7 (-6.0–2.8)	-2.3 (-6.6–2.2)
MiDP	2.1 (0.5–3.8)	2.4 (0.7–4.1)	2.2 (0.5–3.9)	2.2 (0.4–4.0)	-0.4 (-3.6–2.9)	-0.8 (-4.1–2.6)	-0.3 (-1.5–0.9)	-0.2 (-1.4–1.0)	2.9 (-0.7–6.5)	2.2 (-1.5–6.0)
cx-MiNP	-0.2 (-1.3–0.9)	0.0 (-1.2–1.1)	-0.1 (-1.2–1.1)	-0.2 (-1.4–1.0)	0.4 (-1.8–2.6)	0.9 (-1.3–3.2)	0.0 (-0.8–0.8)	0.0 (-0.8–0.8)	-0.7 (-3.0–1.7)	-0.9 (-3.3–1.5)
Σ primary	-2.5 (-4.5–0.4)	-1.9 (-4.1–0.4)	-1.6 (-3.8–0.5)	-2.2 (-4.5–0.3)	0.2 (-3.9–4.5)	3.1 (-1.4–7.8)	-0.3 (-1.8–1.3)	-0.3 (-1.9–1.4)	0.8 (-3.8–5.6)	-1.4 (-6.3–3.7)
Σ secondary	0.0 (-2.9–2.9)	-0.8 (-3.7–2.1)	-2.1 (-5.0–0.8)	-2.4 (-5.4–0.6)	2.3 (-3.3–8.3)	2.4 (-3.2–8.4)	-1.7 (-3.7–0.4)	-1.2 (-3.1–0.8)	-5.9 (-11.4–0.0)	-5 (-10.6–1.0)

^aModels were adjusted for maternal smoking during pregnancy [Y/N], maternal age at delivery, gestational week at maternal serum sampling, smoking habits [non-smoker, occasionally, daily], and total body fat percentage of the young man.

APD, anopenile distance; ASD, anoscrotal distance; CI, confidence interval. Phthalate metabolite abbreviations are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Σ primary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σ secondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP.

Effect estimates (β) have the unit percentage and should be interpreted as the median change in the outcome when the serum concentration of the phthalate metabolite doubles. Significant associations are highlighted in bold.

Supplementary Table 7 Maternal serum concentration of phthalate metabolites and semen parameters in adult sons

	Semen volume		Concentration		Total sperm count		Progressive motility (%)		Normal morphology (%)	
	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI) ^a
MEP	1.3 (-3.5–6.5)	2.5 (-2.5–7.8)	-2.2 (-9.8–6.0)	-0.9 (-9.1–8.1)	-0.9 (-10.3–9.5)	1.6 (-8.2–12.5)	0.7 (-0.8–2.2)	1.0 (-0.6–2.6)	0.1 (-0.3–0.4)	0.1 (-0.2–0.5)
MiBP	1.6 (-6.7–10.6)	2.9 (-6.2–12.9)	-1.6 (-14.4–13.1)	-5.0 (-19.0–11.3)	-0.1 (-15.9–18.7)	-2.3 (-18.9–17.8)	-0.7 (-3.3–1.9)	-2.0 (-4.9–1.0)	-0.6 (-1.2–0.1)	-1.1 (-1.8–(-0.4))
2OH-MiBP	1.0 (-10.8–14.4)	2.0 (-9.6–15.1)	5.7 (-13.8–29.5)	4.8 (-14.8–28.9)	6.8 (-16.9–37.3)	6.9 (-16.1–36.3)	0.5 (-3.3–4.4)	0.2 (-3.7–4.0)	0.0 (-0.9–1.0)	0.2 (-0.7–1.2)
MnBP	2.3 (-2.5–7.3)	3.5 (-2.2–9.4)	1.6 (-6.0–9.9)	2.0 (-7.4–12.4)	4.0 (-5.6–14.6)	5.5 (-5.8–18.2)	-0.1 (-1.6–1.3)	-1.1 (-2.9–0.7)	-0.1 (-0.4–0.3)	-0.4 (-0.8–0.1)
MEHP	14.5 (2.8–27.5)	9.3 (-2.5–22.4)	0.3 (-16.4–20.3)	-3.9 (-21.1–17.0)	14.9 (-8.1–43.5)	5.0 (-16.7–32.3)	-0.8 (-4.2–2.6)	-0.9 (-4.6–2.8)	-0.7 (-1.5–0.1)	-0.8 (-1.7–0.0)
5cx-MEPP	-0.7 (-11.4–11.3)	1.4 (-9.2–13.3)	-3.5 (-19.9–16.2)	-0.5 (-17.7–20.3)	-4.2 (-23.9–20.6)	0.9 (-19.2–26.1)	1.5 (-2.0–5.0)	1.7 (-1.8–5.3)	0.2 (-0.6–1.1)	0.2 (-0.6–1.1)
2cx-MMHP	4.7 (-5.0–15.3)	5.3 (-4.3–15.9)	1.8 (-13.2–19.3)	8.2 (-8.2–27.5)	6.5 (-12.4–29.6)	13.9 (-5.9–38)	1.2 (-1.8–4.2)	2.2 (-0.9–5.3)	0.2 (-0.5–0.9)	0.3 (-0.4–1.0)
MiNP	0.0 (-8.6–9.5)	-0.9 (-9.5–8.6)	-3.5 (-16.7–11.9)	-2.3 (-16.4–14.3)	-3.4 (-19.5–15.9)	-3.1 (-19.3–16.4)	-2.8 (-5.5–0.1)	-2.2 (-5.3–0.8)	-0.7 (-1.4–(-0.02))	-0.7 (-1.4–(-0.03))
cx-MiOP	-4.2 (-13–5.5)	-4.6 (-13.1–4.7)	1.7 (-13.2–19.2)	4.7 (-10.7–22.9)	-2.6 (-19.9–18.4)	-0.1 (-17.2–20.6)	-0.9 (-3.9–2.1)	-0.8 (-3.8–2.1)	-0.5 (-1.2–0.2)	-0.4 (-1.1–0.4)
MiDP	-1.1 (-8.2–6.6)	-2.4 (-9.3–4.9)	4.2 (-7.7–17.7)	4.4 (-7.8–18.2)	3.1 (-11.3–19.8)	1.9 (-12.0–17.9)	-0.5 (-2.8–1.8)	1.0 (-1.4–3.4)	0.1 (-0.5–0.6)	0.2 (-0.3–0.8)
cx-MiNP	-3.6 (-8.3–1.3)	-4.1 (-8.7–0.6)	-2.0 (-9.7–6.3)	-1.7 (-9.6–6.9)	-5.6 (-14.6–4.4)	-5.8 (-14.5–3.9)	-1.4 (-2.9–0.1)	-1.8 (-3.3–(-0.4))	-0.3 (-0.6–0.1)	-0.3 (-0.7–0.0)
Σ primary	6.1 (-3.2–16.3)	7.5 (-2.2–18.1)	-1.2 (-15.1–15)	-2.5 (-17.3–14.9)	4.8 (-13.1–26.4)	4.8 (-13.6–27.1)	-0.3 (-3.2–2.5)	-1.2 (-4.3–1.8)	-0.3 (-1.0–0.4)	-0.5 (-1.2–0.3)
Σ secondary	-7.0 (-18.3–5.8)	-6.1 (-17.0–6.3)	-2.6 (-21.2–20.4)	1.4 (-18.1–25.5)	-9.4 (-30.2–17.6)	-4.8 (-25.9–22.3)	-1.9 (-5.9–2.0)	-2.1 (-6.0–1.9)	-0.7 (-1.7–0.3)	-0.6 (-1.6–0.3)

^aModels were adjusted for maternal smoking during pregnancy [Y/N], maternal age at delivery, gestational week at maternal serum sampling, smoking habits [non-smoker, occasionally, daily], total body fat percentage of the young man and time of day for serum sampling.

CI, confidence interval. Phthalate metabolite abbreviations are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Σ primary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σ secondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP.

Effect estimates (β) have the unit percentage and should be interpreted as the median change in the outcome when the serum concentration of the phthalate metabolite doubles. Please note that as motility and morphology counts were included in models untransformed, the shown effect estimates are to be interpreted as the absolute change (percentage points) when exposure doubles. Significant associations are highlighted in bold.

Supplementary Figure 1 Maternal serum concentration of phthalate metabolites and reproductive hormone concentrations (FSH/Sertoli cell axis, estradiol and growth factors) in adult sons

FSH, follicle-stimulating hormone; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor; IGFBP-3, insulin-like growth factor-binding protein 3. Abbreviations of phthalate metabolites are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Σ primary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σ secondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP. The plots show effect estimates from linear regression analyses. Estimates are shown as the percent change in outcome when exposure doubles.

Supplementary Figure 2 Maternal serum concentration of phthalate metabolites and semen parameters in adult sons

Abbreviations of phthalate metabolites are presented in Supplementary Table 1. Σ primary is the molar sum of MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MEHP, MiNP, and MiDP expressed as MnBP; Σ secondary is the molar sum of 2OH-MiNP, 5cx-MEPP, 2cx-MMHP, cx-MiOP, and cx-MiNP expressed as 2OH-MiNP. The plots show effect estimates from linear regression analyses. Estimates are shown as the percent change in outcome when exposure doubles. Please note that motility and morphology were included in models untransformed; the effect estimates reflect the absolute change (percentage points) in these measures when exposure doubles.